

Popular Article

Addressing One Health Issues as An Environmental Concern

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Abstract

The environmental factors play an essential role in public health, yet, to date, it has been an under-utilized partner for health in most of the countries. While authorities of human and animal health and environment sectors may not be aware of the benefits of collaboration of these units together as a “ONE HEALTH” concept, which will hopefully able to achieve its full potential in local, national and global levels. Because animals and humans have shared risk to health and changing environments, it seems logical to expand the perspectives of public health beyond a single species, to detect and manage emerging global health threats.

Introduction

While the whole world still lags in coming up with efficient regulation based on the development versus environment database, there is an increasing awareness in global arena that climate change needs to be checked to control its effect on the environment. So, the solutions to these global environmental issues, require efforts at international issues. Mitigating the effects of climate change, emerging pathogens, toxicant releases, and changes in the built environment requires a retooling of public health resources and capabilities across multiple species.

Emergence of infectious diseases:

Animals and people often can be affected by many of the same diseases and environmental issues. Some diseases called, zoonotic diseases, can spread between animals and people. More than half of all infections people one can get, can be spread by animals- a few examples include rabies, salmonellosis, brucellosis, anthrax, Q fever and West Nile virus, due to environmental issues like harmful algal blooms or lead contamination which affect public health in common terms. Of these, approximately three-quarters emerged from wildlife, such as HIV/AIDS, SARS, and Ebola. Antimicrobial resistance is another emerging threat to the health of the dwellings of the society, and resistant germs often spread through our shared environment.

As Earth's population grows, our connection with animals and the environment changes: people live close together, travel more often around the globe, alter the environment and have different relationships with animals and environment for companionship, education, food and various purposes. At the same time, the environment represents an important role in human exposure to polluted air, noise and hazardous chemicals. Noise exposure from transport sources and industry can lead to annoyance, sleep disturbance and relatively increases the risk of hypertension and cardiovascular diseases. The properties of certain hazardous chemicals cause them to persist in the environment and bioaccumulate in the food chain, which means there will be a considerable time lag before reductions in emissions translate into reduced exposure. This raises concerns about the health effects of exposure to mixtures of chemicals over our lifetime, in particular during vulnerable life stages, such as early childhood, pregnancy and old age.

Challenges

In their report on preventing diseases through healthy environments, the World Health Organization (WHO) estimates that environmental stressors are responsible for 12-18% of all deaths in the 53 countries of the WHO Europe Region. Air pollution is the single largest environmental health risk in Europe, and is associated with heart disease, stroke, lung disease and lung cancer. Exposure to air pollution is estimated to result in over 400,000 premature deaths in the European Union each year. The impacts of climate change also pose immediate threats to health, in terms of heat waves and shifts in the patterns of infectious diseases and allergens. A growing body of evidence suggests that environmental risks are not evenly distributed across society, but rather disproportionately affect socially disadvantaged and vulnerable population groups. An individual's socioeconomic status influences their exposure to environmental stressors, since poorer people are most likely to live in degraded environments. Socially disadvantaged people may be more sensitive to the impacts not environmental stressors due to pre-existing health conditions, poor nutritional status and specific behaviours, such as smoking or inactivity. They may also face constraints in adapting to and avoiding environmental risks. so, "One Health" can be a beneficial initiative to tackle the web of interlinked health issues.

Measures to be taken to enhance "ONE HEALTH" issues

By utilizing data, expertise, and management approaches in the environment and natural resources sector, we can enhance our understanding of the root causes of diseases, better account for complexity of environmental factors, and ultimately encourage protection of resources to benefit health terms. Improving the quality of the environment in key areas such as air, water and noise can prevent diseases and improve human health. Data that should be our prime importance are climate forecasting to detect climate sensitive vector borne diseases, water quality monitoring of every kind of private and public localities, check upon

dynamics (ecological) and drivers (anthropogenic) that leads to vector borne and zoonotic emergence, sentinel monitoring of wildlife to identify diseases before potential spill over to other components of ecosystem etc. Involving environmental and natural resources professionals, can result in a comprehensive picture of the factors that affect community health as a wholesome unit. The environmental sector plays a key role in early warning, detection, and identifying of diseases risk as well as in response. So, Environmental authorities-controlled strategies should be adopted to balance threats that cause harm to ecosystem can be a checked measure. It may also detect and monitor diseases in wildlife that do not pose a direct threat to humans. However, even non-zoonotic diseases may have implications for the health and functioning of ecosystems in ways that can indirectly affect humans such as pest control, pollution etc. Expertise and infrastructure from environmental services are the need of the hour as valuable components of health security, and should include in natural resources to maximize the protection of public health.

Conclusion

In 2014, parties to the United Nations Convention on Biological Diversity agreed to recognize “the value of the ‘ONE HEALTH’ approach to address the cross cutting of interconnected biodiversity and human health, as an integrated approach consistent with the ecosystem approach (decision V/6) that integrates the complex relationships between humans, microorganisms, animals, plants, agriculture, wildlife, and the environment. So, a global approach is needed to promote environmental sector as a valuable contributor in the population health and well-being, particularly in “health security” efforts to prevent and prepare for endemic, epidemic, pandemic threats.

References

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